

Acid-catalysed Hydrolysis of Methyl Acetate in Micellar Phase

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Micellar systems catalyse and retard the rate of chemical reactions¹. We reported earlier the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in surfactant media². The present study deals with the findings on the hydrolysis of methyl acetate in micellar phase in order to understand the nature of interactions responsible for catalytic and inhibitory effects of micelles on the rate of hydrolysis of simple carboxylic esters.

Results and Discussion

The rate of hydrolysis of methyl acetate in aqueous hydrochloric acid has been measured in presence of cationic and anionic surfactants at 30° and with non-ionic surfactant at 35°. Cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB), sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS) and Triton-x-100 are cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants respectively. The pseudo-first order rate constants are given in Table 1. The thermodynamic parameters and the rate constants are given in Table 2. The rate data (Table 3) correspond to the effect on variation of concentrations of ester and acid on the rate of hydrolysis. The results of salt-effect of NaCl on the hydrolytic reaction are given in Table 4.

The proton transfer mechanistic scheme³ is applicable to this hydrolytic reaction where an acylcarbonium ion intermediate is formed and it reacts with water to give the resulting carboxylic acid. The change in the rate of hydrolysis in micellar media can also be explained through the acylcarbonium ion intermediate. An identical distribution model developed by Menger and Portnoy⁴ used for enzymatic catalysis, can be fitted to this hydrolysis in surfactant medium as follows :

where, S_n is the surfactant aggregate (micelle), E the ester, $S_n E$ the micelle-ester complex, K_a the association constant, and k_w and k_m are the first order rate constants for the hydrolysis in the bulk phase and micellar pseudo-phase respectively.

Effect of cationic surfactant (CTAB) : It is observed that on increasing the concentration of CTAB in the reaction media above its CMC, the rate of hydrolysis gradually decreases upto 0.07 M. CTAB forms cationic micelles beyond its CMC and the number of micelles increases on increasing CTAB concentration. Due to hydrophobic interaction of micellar core, methyl acetate molecules get solubilised into it to certain extent, and transfer of proton to the ester molecule to initiate the hydrolysis is hindered for electrostatic repulsion between the proton and positive head groups of these micelles. In micellar pseudo-phase hydrolysis is hindered whereas in bulk phase it occurs. These are the causes for the gradual decrease in the k_1 values (Table 1). Chevion *et al.*⁵ observed similar effect of cationic surfactants on acid-catalysed hydrolysis of *p*-nitrophenyl propionate.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR ACID-CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL ACETATE IN VARYING CONCENTRATIONS OF SURFACTANTS IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM AT 30°

[Methyl acetate] = 0.251 M, [HCl] = 0.45 M								
[CTAB] M	0.00	0.002	0.004	0.008	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.07
k_1 (10 ⁵ s ⁻¹)	8.32	8.01	7.83	7.54	7.33	7.11	6.91	6.74
	± 0.0028	± 0.0024	± 0.0079	± 0.0089	± 0.0046	± 0.0022	± 0.0051	± 0.0027
[NaLS] (M)	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07
k_1 (10 ⁵ s ⁻¹)	8.32	8.51	8.93	9.14	9.31	9.58	9.92	9.51
	± 0.0028	± 0.005	± 0.0069	± 0.0034	± 0.006	± 0.0011	± 0.0012	± 0.0021
[Triton-x-100] (ml/50 ml)	0.00	0.50	0.60	0.70	0.80	0.90	1.00	1.10
k_1 (10 ⁵ s ⁻¹)	13.25	13.13	13.00	12.97	13.10	13.15	13.00	13.20
	± 0.0047	± 0.0030	± 0.0085	± 0.0025	± 0.0098	± 0.0064	± 0.0043	± 0.0053

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON ACID-CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL ACETATE IN ABSENCE AND IN PRESENCE OF SURFACTANTS
[Methylacetate] = 0.251 M, [HCl] = 0.45 M

25°	$k_1 (\times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1})$ at			E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹ at 30°	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK mol ⁻¹ at 30°	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹ at 30°
	30°	35°	40°				
	[Surfactant] = 0.00 M						
6.63 ± 0.0058	8.32 ± 0.0028	13.25 ± 0.0047	15.33 ± 0.0046	48.61 ± 0.039	46.09	68.97	66.98
	[CTAB] = 0.02 M						
5.75 ± 0.0030	7.11 ± 0.0022	12.35 ± 0.0039	13.85 ± 0.001	50.03 ± 0.051	47.52	65.29	67.30
	[NaLS] = 0.05 M						
8.12 ± 0.0046	9.58 ± 0.0011	16.27 ± 0.0042	18.66 ± 0.0034	45.81 ± 0.049	43.30	76.77	66.56

TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANTS OF ACID-CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL ACETATE AT VARYING CONCENTRATIONS OF ESTER AND ACID IN ABSENCE AND IN PRESENCE OF SURFACTANTS AT 30°

[Ester] M	[Surfactant] = 0.00 M	[CTAB] = 0.02 M	[NaLS] = 0.05 M
	$k_1 (\times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1})$		
0.2510	8.32 ± 0.0028	7.11 ± 0.0022	9.58 ± 0.0011
0.3765	8.61 ± 0.01	7.45 ± 0.0036	9.16 ± 0.0014
0.5020	9.02 ± 0.0051	8.01 ± 0.0059	8.44 ± 0.0047
0.6275	9.53 ± 0.0027	8.33 ± 0.0012	8.02 ± 0.0047
	[Ester] = 0.251 M, Temp. = 35°		
[HCl] M			
0.45	13.25 ± 0.0047	12.35 ± 0.0039	16.27 ± 0.0042
0.50	16.31 ± 0.016	14.72 ± 0.01	19.23 ± 0.013
0.55	19.18 ± 0.016	16.88 ± 0.0073	21.61 ± 0.014
0.60	20.80 ± 0.010	19.18 ± 0.0074	23.14 ± 0.017

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SALT ON THE ACID-CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL ACETATE IN ABSENCE AND IN PRESENCE OF SURFACTANTS AT 30°

[Methyl acetate] = 0.251 M, [HCl] = 0.45 M	$k^{-1} (\times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1})$ at [NaCl] in M		
	0.40	0.50	0.60
	[Surfactant] = 0.00 M		
8.32 ± 0.0028	7.95 ± 0.0052	7.83 ± 0.0072	7.73 ± 0.0077
	[CTAB] = 0.02 M		
7.11 ± 0.0022	6.63 ± 0.0077	6.50 ± 0.0035	6.31 ± 0.0076
	[NaLS] = 0.05 M		
9.58 ± 0.0011	9.31 ± 0.014	9.11 ± 0.0030	8.93 ± 0.0042

Effect of anionic surfactant (NaLS) : In presence of varying concentrations of anionic surfactant NaLS beyond its CMC in the reaction mixture the hydrolysis of methyl acetate increases. The maximum value of rate constant is observed at 0.06 M of NaLS (Table 1). The catalytic effect is due to the solubilisation of ester molecules in the micelles for the hydrophobic interaction and presence of proton in

the Stern layer for electrostatic attraction. The rate enhancement is further assisted by the stabilisation of acylcarbonium ion intermediate in the Stern layer of anionic micelles. With increasing concentration of surfactant, the number of micelles increases and hence the rate. The rate dropping down after reaching a maximum value may be due to distribution of protons in large number of micelles when its concentration decreases in the Stern layer⁴. A plot of k_{obs} vs [NaLS] is found to be linear upto a concentration of 0.06 M. A mathematical relation based on Menger-Portnoy distribution model is as follows :

$$\frac{1}{k_w - k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k_w - k_m} + \left[\frac{N}{K_a (k_w - k_m)} \right] \frac{1}{(C_D - \text{CMC})} \quad (1)$$

where, k_{obs} is the observed rate constant, N the aggregation number, C_D the surfactant concentration and CMC the critical micelle concentration. Other notations are described earlier. The k_{obs} data with varying concentration of NaLS upto 0.06 M fitted to the above relation. The results fit well except at low concentration of NaLS, below 0.03 M. From the intercept and slope of the plot $1/(k_w - k_{\text{obs}})$ vs $1/(C_D - \text{CMC})$ and using the aggregation number (N) value of NaLS¹ to be 62, the constants K_a and k_m were evaluated to be 9.08×10^2 and $11.65 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. In case of ethyl acetate hydrolysis there was deviation in Menger-Portnoy relation only beyond 0.06 M NaLS².

Effect of nonionic surfactant : Effect of a nonionic surfactant Triton-x-100 in varying concentration beyond its CMC on acid hydrolysis of methyl acetate at 35° has been examined and results are given in Table 1. It seems this nonionic surfactant has no effect on the rate of hydrolysis. It is also evident from literature¹ that such surfactants either decrease the rate or have no effect at all on the hydrolysis of carboxylic esters.

Effect of temperature : In Table 2 the values of rate constants at varying temperatures in absence and presence of surfactants have been given. The rate has increased with rise in temperature in all the cases. Different thermodynamic quantities have been calculated using Arrhenius plot, Eyrings and Gibbs-Helmholtz equations. It is observed that activation energy and enthalpy of the reaction increased in 0.02 M CTAB and decreased in 0.05 M NaLS in comparison to that in absence of surfactant. This indicates greater stability of transition state in NaLS and its destabilisation in CTAB micelles. All negative entropy of activation and free energy of activation values also show similar trends as stated above, indicating the degree of mobility and stability of transition state respectively.

Effect of ester and acid concentration : Effect of varying concentration of ester on the reaction rate at fixed concentration of acid and vice versa have been studied in absence of surfactant and in presence of 0.02 M CTAB and

0.05 M NaLS (Table 3). There was rate enhancement in absence and presence of CTAB; rate retardation with NaLS on increasing [ester], whereas on increasing [acid] the rate acceleration has been observed in all cases. In such acid-catalytic reactions the rate is directly proportional to the [acid] and to the [ester]. The rate of this type of hydrolytic reactions depends a great deal on the values of equilibrium

constant ($S + H^+ \xrightleftharpoons{K_{eq}} SH^+$) and the relative concentrations of H^+ and S (ester)⁶. The decrease in rate constant on increasing [ester] in presence of 0.05 M NaLS may be due to saturation of anionic micellar phase with the substrate as its concentration increases⁷. At 30° and at about 0.5 M [ester] the rate of hydrolysis of ethyl acetate is faster than methyl acetate in absence and presence of 0.02 M CTAB.

Effect of sodium chloride as additive : On addition of sodium chloride in increasing concentrations, the rate of hydrolysis is inhibited in absence and presence of surfactants. In absence of surfactant, this retardation may be due to ion-dipole interactions between the added ions and reacting molecules and similar interactions involving other constituents of the system⁸. In NaLS micellar system hydrolysis rate acceleration was seen, but in presence of both NaLS and NaCl the inhibition of rate of hydrolysis has been observed. This may be due to the increased concentration of counter ion (Na^+) in the Stern layer and displacement of hydrogen ion from the micellar surface by the electrolyte⁹. Hydrolytic rate retardation in CTAB micelles is further retarded in presence of NaCl.

Experimental

Methylacetate (b.p. 57°, German make) was purified¹⁰ before use. Purification of other chemicals, the method of kinetic measurement and calculations were the same as described earlier².

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